

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THEMATOLOGY OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK EPIC POEMS: BEOWULF AND ALPOMISH

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Abstract

This article deals with the thematic aspect of Old English and Uzbek epic poems focusing on theoretical assumptions of thematology, types of themes from comparative perspectives in Anglo Saxon epic poem Beowulf and Old Turkic/Uzbek epic poem Alpomish.

Keywords: thematology, thematics, epic poems, Anglo Saxon Literature, Old Turkic literature

Thematology is the comparative study of themes in various literary works. "The study of literary themes, particularly those of a geographically distributed culture." It is a comparative study of literary works as they relate to other literary works outside of their national borders in terms of themes. It is a more focused and limited study in the field of comparative literary studies. [2, p. 1408-1410]

The term 'Thematology' or 'Thematics' find by American Comparatist called Harry Levin.[3, p.359] The term has yet to be included in the Oxford English Dictionary, but it has gained popularity among comparatists. Thematology has recently emerged as an important branch of comparative literature. Thematology is the study of themes and motifs. Both terms are fundamentally distinct; however, they have been used interchangeably. Themes are recurring elements, but they are associated with the subject matter of a literary work. Themes are associated with both form and content in contemporary criticism. A theme is always a subject, but a subject cannot always become a theme. It is communicated indirectly through events, images, or symbols. It is understood not by the number of images but by their meaningful arrangement within the text. It necessitates a pattern and allows for the completion of the entire work. A motif is always a recurring element. It could be an incident, a device, or a formula. For instance, a despicable lady transforms into a charming princess, which is a standard formula in folklore.

Thematology is primarily concerned with the content or subject matter of literature. Though it literally means "the study of themes," it actually covers a wide range of topics such as situation, type, motive, topos, and so on. Thematic analysis is a logical and traditional method of comparing authors and literatures. As a result, it is fundamentally and nearly a part of analogy study. Motives and types are the two types of themes. A theme is a pathway for the progression of ideas into literature, which it both invites and facilitates. In comparative literature, themes play an important role. Many nations have provided facilities and encouragement to go for the translation of the most important documents from one literature to another based on themes.

The following are some reasons why thematology is beneficial to comparatists: 1) It allows a comparatist to identify the different types of subjects that different writers favor; 2) It helps a comparatist to determine what kind of writer choose subjects that are covered in various time periods; 3) We can investigate the peculiar issues of a time period, a group, or a society and how they affect writers' personalities and ways of thinking; 4) It aids in our understanding of how certain subjects may necessitate various stylistic motifs; 5) It also explains how various topics are more compatible with particular genres. City themes, for instance, are associated with the novel genre.

This essay provides a summary of the themes found in both English and Uzbek epic poetry. One of the most significant pieces of Old English literature, Beowulf has generated a great deal of academic debate, discussion, and research. The word "Alpomish" is a wonderful representation of the Uzbek people's lengthy history.

An Old English epic poem called Beowulf has 3182 lines that use alliteration. It is considered to be one of the most significant pieces of Old English literature and has generated a great deal of academic debate, theory, and research. Scholars disagree on the composition's chronology; the only dating that is confirmed is to the manuscript, which was created between 975 and 1025.

Beowulf, the protagonist of the poem, journeys to Denmark from his native Geatland to aid King Hrothgar, who is being harassed by the monster Grendel. After a bloody battle, Beowulf vanquishes Grendel, but he then has to face Grendel's mother, who is seeking retribution for the death of her son. Following his victory against her, Beowulf makes his way back to Geatland, where he is crowned king and must take on one last foe: a dragon that is frightening his people. Although killing the dragon, Beowulf suffers a fatal injury.

Several themes typical to the heroic epic tradition are explored in the story of Beowulf, including valor, honor, loyalty, and the conflict between good and evil. Beowulf is portrayed as a skillful and courageous warrior who, with strength and courage, can defeat even the most terrifying adversaries. He is also demonstrated to

be a devoted and noble leader who is prepared to risk his own life to defend his followers.

Beowulf has had a tremendous impact on English literature and popular culture in addition to its literary and cultural importance. Several other pieces of fiction, films, and other forms of media have been influenced by one of the most significant pieces of Old English literature. Beowulf has endured as a representation of bravery and heroism, and readers and viewers are still drawn to him today.[4,5]

The literary heritage of the Uzbek people is one that has been passed down through the generations. It is thought to have its roots in Central Asia and is regarded as a significant contribution to the Turkic literary heritage. Epics from the Karakalpak, Kazakh, and Altai dialects of "Alpomish" as well as stories and fairy tales from the Bashkir and Tatar dialects have all reached us. The Bashkirs referred to it as "Alpamisha and Barsin hiluu," while the Uzbeks termed it "Alpomish," the Karakalpaks "Alpamis," the Kazakhs "Alpomish batir," the Altaians "Apip-Manash," the Kazan Tatars "Alpamsha," and the Kazakhs "Alpomish batir." The Epic of Alpamysh is one example of a work included in the tradition that serves as a symbol of valor, honor, and courage.[1]

A young man sets out on a quest to establish his value and win back his lost respect in The Epic of Alpamysh, a heroic poetry. A strong and evil monarch, a perilous mountain, and a terrible monster are some of the difficulties that Alpamysh encounters on his mission. Additionally, he must overcome his own doubts and concerns as well as numerous tests of devotion and bravery. He eventually defeats evil and is reunited with his beloved.[6]

Among the Kungiro, sixteen clans were known as Dobonbi in ancient times. Dobonbi had a child named Olpinbi. Olpinbi was the father of two sons. He gave the elder Boybori and the younger Boysari their names. Dobonbi divides his country's wealth into two parts, which he refers to as Kungiro and Boysun. He assigned one to his elder son, Boybori, and the other to his younger son, Boysari. Boybori and Boysari are oppressed by their inability to have children. Finally, both Boybori and Boysari's wives will become pregnant. Boybori plans to name the child Khakimbek. Boysari will be a girl, and her name will be Barchin. The brothers have agreed to be godparents to our children when they grow up. Khakimbek grew up as a wrestler; from a young age, his peers began to refer to him as a wrestler, i.e., "Alp." Barchin means both beautiful and intelligent.

Boybori and Boysari had a disagreement one day. This was because Boybori demanded zakat from his brother Boysari. Boysari and his clan seek refuge with the Kalmyks after refusing to pay zakat to his brother. The Boysari cattle show the Kalmaks' cultivated lands along the way. Kalmakhshah, who is furious, regards Boysari as enemies. There are 90 young men in Kalmakhshah who fall in love with Barchin. Barchin attempts to protect herself from the Kalmyk ruler's violence. When she realizes her father is in a difficult situation, she employs her wisdom to get him out of it and

imposes four conditions. It indicates that she is prepared to marry the person who the person who meets the requirements. The first condition was to strike a coin from a thousand paces away; the second was to wrestle 90 mountains; the third was not to break the bow when shooting a bow; and the fourth was to win a race. He returns Barchin to his country, Kungiro, after fulfilling the conditions set by Barchin and after several more adventures. It accomplishes its goal. [8-12]

The topics in both epic poems are similar:

1) The warrior mentality, as well as the ideals of bravery, loyalty, and honor in battle, is one of the most prevalent themes throughout both poems. It is possible to interpret this exaltation of the warrior mentality as a reaction to the unpredictability and violence of the time.

2) The influence of fate is a further crucial subject. The idea that fate predetermines events and that people have little influence over their own destinies is explored in many of the works of the time. This subject might be interpreted as a reflection of the period's feeling of instability and unpredictability.

3) Kinship: In Anglo-Saxon and Turkic society, family and familial relationships were very important, and this is represented in a lot of the literature from the time. Several literary pieces, including Beowulf and Alpomish, tackle the theme of loyalty to one's lord or family and the significance of upholding familial relationships.

4) Wisdom: Much of the literature from the time period reflects the high emphasis placed on wisdom and knowledge in Anglo-Saxon and Turkic cultures.

5) Women: Despite the patriarchal nature of Anglo-Saxon and Turkic society, women do appear occasionally in Old English and Uzbek literature. These epic poems provide representations of powerful, independent women who are able to resist misfortune and hardship. The supernatural: These poems are also known for their use of supernatural elements, such as monsters, dragons, and ghosts. These elements often serve as a metaphor for the challenges and struggles that humans face in their lives.

6) Heroism: The heroic epic tradition frequently features heroic figures who face formidable obstacles and surmount them with strength, bravery, and cunning.

7) Honor: The value of honor is frequently discussed in heroic epics, both as a personal virtue and as a social duty. Characters could be motivated by a desire to protect their honor or to redeem themselves after a mistake.

8) Loyalty: Characters may be required to prove their loyalty to their family, their country, or their leader, making loyalty a prominent topic in the heroic epic genre. Love and sacrifice: Many heroic epics explore the theme of love and sacrifice, as characters must choose between their own desires and the greater good. Sacrifice may take many forms, including giving up one's life, one's reputation, or one's dreams.

9) The conflict between good and evil: A fight between opposing forces, such as good and evil, light and dark, or order and chaos, is a common theme in heroic epics. Characters may be asked to stand up for what is

right, even if it puts them in grave risk or forces them to make unpopular decisions.

Consequently, Old English and Uzbek literature is extensive and varied. The literature still inspires and captivates readers and academics today because it depicts the ideals, perspectives, and life experiences of the Anglo-Saxon people. The heroic epic tradition examines the various ways that people, groups, and civilizations deal with problems and make an effort to uphold their beliefs and values. Insights into the human experience throughout history can be found in the timeless themes of heroism, honor, loyalty, love, sacrifice, and the conflict between good and evil. These themes continue to ring true with readers and viewers today.

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